

Computer Program in C Programming Language for Calculating the Value of Euler Product equal to the Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: This paper presents a novel idea to compute the product of geometric series with prime numbers. The product of geometric series with prime numbers plays a vital in the sum of natural numbers, harmonic series, and the Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function. Also, in this article, computer program in C programming language is introduced to compute the value of Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-20] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [11]. Also, the product of geometric series [21-37] with prime numbers plays a vital in the sum of natural numbers, harmonic series, and the Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function [38-40].

2. Product of Geometric Series equal to Harmonic Series

Theorem 2.1: The product of geometric series on primes is equal to the sum of natural numbers.

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_i^j \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n, \text{ where } p_i \text{ is the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ prime number.}$$

Proof. Let us prove the above theorem as follows:

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_i^j \right) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_1^j \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_2^j \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_3^j \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_4^j \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_5^j \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_6^j \times \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_i^j \right) = (1 + p_1 + p_1^2 + p_1^3 + \dots)(1 + p_2 + p_2^2 + p_2^3 + \dots) \dots \quad (2)$$

By simplifying the expression (2), we get

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_i^j \right) = 1 + \sum_{1 \leq i} p_i + \sum_{1 \leq i < j} p_i p_j + \sum_{1 \leq i < j < k} p_i p_j p_k + \dots \quad (3)$$

By rearranging the expansion (3), we obtain

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_i^j \right) = 1 + p_1 + p_2 + p_1 p_1 + p_3 + p_1 p_2 + p_4 + p_1 p_1 p_1 + p_2 p_2 + \dots \quad (4)$$

where $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3, p_3 = 5, p_4 = 7, p_5 = 11, p_6 = 13, p_7 = 17, p_8 = 19, \dots$

By substituting the numerical values of p_i in the equation (4), we conclude that

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_i^j \right) = 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n. \quad (5)$$

Hence, proved.

3. Product of Geometric Series equal to Harmonic Series

Theorem 3.1: The product of geometric series equal to the harmonic series shown below:

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}, \text{ where } p_i \text{ is the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ prime number.}$$

Proof. Let us prove the above theorem as follows:

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} \right) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_1^j} \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_2^j} \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_3^j} \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_4^j} \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_5^j} \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_6^j} \times \dots \quad (6)$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} \right) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_1^2} + \frac{1}{p_1^3} + \dots \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_2} + \frac{1}{p_2^2} + \frac{1}{p_2^3} + \dots \right) \dots \quad (7)$$

By simplifying the expression (7), we get

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} \right) = 1 + \sum_{1 \leq i} \frac{1}{p_i} + \sum_{1 \leq i \leq j} \frac{1}{p_i p_j} + \sum_{1 \leq i \leq j \leq k} \frac{1}{p_i p_j p_k} + \dots \quad (8)$$

By rearranging the expansion (8), we obtain

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} \right) = 1 + \frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2} + \frac{1}{p_1 p_1} + \frac{1}{p_3} + \frac{1}{p_1 p_2} + \frac{1}{p_4} + \frac{1}{p_1 p_1 p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2 p_2} + \dots \quad (9)$$

By substituting the numerical values of p_i in the equation (9), we conclude that

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} \right) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}. \quad (10)$$

Hence, proved.

Note that $\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}$ since $\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_i^j} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i}}$. (11)

4. Euler Product for Riemann Zeta Function

The Euler product for the Riemann zeta function is given below:

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - p_i^{-s}}$ is the Euler product and p_i is the i^{th} prime.

Let us prove the Euler infinite product (12) as follows:

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_1^s}} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_2^s}} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_3^s}} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_4^s}} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_5^s}} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_6^s}} \times \dots \quad (13)$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_1^{is}} \times \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_2^{is}} \times \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_3^{is}} \times \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_4^{is}} \times \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_5^{is}} \times \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_6^{is}} \times \dots \quad (14)$$

From the equations (10) and (11), we conclude

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}}.$$

5. C Program for Euler product.

C program for computing the following Euler product is given below:

$$\zeta(2) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^2}}.$$

```
#include<stdio.h>
void main(){
    int i, num, n=40000, count;
    float Euler=1;
    for(num = 1;num<=n;num++){
        count = 0;
        for(i=2;i<=num/2;i++){
            if(num%i==0){
                count++;
                break;
            }
        }
        if(count==0 && num!= 1)
            Euler=Euler*num*num/(num*num-1);
    }
    printf("The value of Euler product with prime numbers between 1 and 40000 is %f.", Euler);
}
```

Output: The value of Euler product with prime numbers between 1 and 40000 is 1.644934.

Conclusion

In this article, computer program in C programming language has been introduced for computing the value of Euler product equal to the Riemann zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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